

Identification of the through-thickness orthotropic stiffness components of thick filament-wound composite tubes in an industrial context

Authors

Dr. Pascal Lava,
Dr. Amar Peshave,
Prof. Fabrice Pierron

Industry collaborators

Dr. Erick Montes de Oca Valle
Dr. Irene Jimenez Fortunato,
Magma Global, UK

Presenter

Dr Isabella M. Jacobsen

Composites tubes, pipes and pressure vessels

<https://www.cf-composites.toray/>

[https://cstoptimum.com/Hydrogen storage](https://cstoptimum.com/Hydrogen%20storage)

Hydrocarbon, water, gas

www.matchid.eu

<https://www.carbon-composite.com/>

Through-thickness properties

- Material Testing 1.0*
 - Statically determinate
 - Strain gauges
- Time consuming
- Effect of curvature?

*Pierron, F., & Grédiac, M. (2021). Towards Material Testing 2.0. A review of test design for identification of constitutive parameters from full-field measurements. *Strain*, 57(1), e12370.

Material Testing 2.0

Heterogeneous test

Digital Image Correlation

Inverse identification

Finite Element Model Updating

The Virtual Fields Method

In the literature...

- Thick glass/epoxy ring from tube, 90° (hoop)

	Q_{rr}	$Q_{\theta\theta}$	$Q_{r\theta}$	Q_{ss}
Reference (GPa)	10	40	3	4
Identified (GPa)	11.4	45.4	2.62	6.78
CV(%) – 9 tests	29	10	29	4

Moulart, R., Avril, S., & Pierron, F. (2006). Identification of the through-thickness rigidities of a thick laminated composite tube. *Composites Part A*, 37(2), 326-336.

Context and present contribution

- MatchID's VFM module
- Extend to cylindrical material coordinates
- New choice of virtual fields
- Verify on synthetic data
- Validate on experiments

Virtual fields selection

- Manually-defined¹

- 😊 • Ease of programming
- 😞 • Suboptimal, boundary condition dependent

- Noise optimized²

- Piecewise expansion³, in cylindrical coordinate systems⁴
- 😊 • Maximum likelihood solution
- 😞 • Complex programming, sensitive to outliers, limited to elasticity

- Sensitivity-based⁵

- 😊 • Piecewise expansion, based on stress sensitivities
- 😞 • Highly flexible, very efficient
- Require more stress computations

First time application to elasticity problems

[1] Pierron, F., Zhavoronok, S., & Grédiac, M. (2000). *Int. J. of Sol. and Struct.*, 37(32), 4437-4453.

[2] Avril, S., Grédiac, M., & Pierron, F. (2004). *Computational Mechanics*, 34(6), 439-452.

[3] Toussaint, E., Grédiac, M., & Pierron, F. (2006). *Int. J. of Mech. Sci.*, 48(3), 256-264.

[4] Moulart, R., Avril, S., & Pierron, F. (2006). *Composites Part A*, 37(2), 326-336.

Test specimen

- Test specimen
 - Carbon/epoxy ring cut from tube, hoop-wound
- Experimental setup

- Blue LEDs
- PointGrey 5 Mpx cameras(2448 x 2048)
- Fujinon 50 mm XA series
- In-house built compression fixture

Images

Laser engraved
250 μm dots

Histogram

Experimental protocol and DIC settings

- Calibration
- Stationary images: 100
 - Averaged reference images
- 5 load steps
 - 460, 892, 1322, 1760 and 2194 N
 - 100 averaged deformed images
 - All used for identification
- DIC setting
 - Subset: 21, step: 1
 - Strain window: 5 (Q4)
 - ZNSSD, affine shape functions, local bicubic splines

Digital Twin (DT): FEDEF Module

MatchID

Metrology beyond colors

Simulated image

Cameras

Simulated image

Balcaen, R., Wittevrongel, L., Reu, P. L., Lava, P., & Debruyne, D. (2017). Stereo-DIC Calibration and Speckle Image Generator Based on FE Formulations. *Experimental Mechanics*, 57(5), 703-718.

Last load step - $\epsilon_{rr} (\mu\epsilon)$

Experimental

FE - DT

Last load step - $\epsilon_{\theta\theta}$ ($\mu\epsilon$)

Experimental

FE - DT

Last load step - $\epsilon_{r\theta}$ ($\mu\epsilon$)

Sensitivity virtual fields

Identification results

- VFM settings:

Strain window	Virtual mesh
5	9 x 9
10	9 x 9
10	6 x 6

All virtual dofs fixed

Horizontal fixed
Vertical: constant

- Virtual boundary conditions

Results

- All load steps (5), all VFM settings (3), 15 results

	E_{rr} (GPa)	$E_{\theta\theta}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{\theta r}$ (-)	$G_{r\theta}$ (GPa)
Mean	7.04	101	0.51	3.09
Coef. Var (%)	7.7	3.0	19	2.2

- Last load step (VFM sensitivity)

	E_{rr} (GPa)	$E_{\theta\theta}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{\theta r}$ (-)	$G_{r\theta}$ (GPa)
Mean	7.82	106	0.54	3.06
Coef. Var (%)	0.2	1.3	8.4	0.9

Identification from Digital Twin

	E_{rr} (GPa)	$E_{\theta\theta}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{\theta r}$ (-)	$G_{r\theta}$ (GPa)
Reference	7.82	106	0.54	3.06
Identified	8.35	157	0.26	3.61
Ref/Id.	0.93	0.67	2.07	0.85

Reason: missing edges*

Amplified by bending deformation

*Rossi, M., & Pierron, F. (2012). *Int. J. of Sol. and Struct.*, 49(3-4), 420-435.

Underway:
data padding
approach

Corrected identified values

	E_{rr} (GPa)	$E_{\theta\theta}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{\theta r}$ (-)	$G_{r\theta}$ (GPa)
Initial	7.82	106	0.54	3.06
Corrected	7.32	71.6	1.12	2.59

Possible shear nonlinearity

Conclusions

- Operational tool for MT2.0 on composites
- Outstanding feature: edge padding (underway)
- Digital Twin:
 - UQ
 - Correction of systematic errors
- Future work
 - Apply to other configurations
 - New standards

	E_{rr} (GPa)	$E_{\theta\theta}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{\theta r}$ (-)	$G_{r\theta}$ (GPa)
Initial	7.82	106	0.54	3.06
Corrected	7.32	71.6	1.12	2.59

Thank you for your attention
isabella.m.jacobsen@matchid.us

